

TETR ARCHs

Transforming Data Reuse in Archaeology

Deliverable 8.2

Digital Resident Outputs Report

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Summary

This Deliverable 8.2, titled *Digital Resident Outputs Report*, describes collaborations with creative practitioners that took place as part of the TETRARCHS project. This includes an explanation of the recruitment process and a discussion of artist involvement at the archaeological excavation sites, before showcasing the presentation of their work at exhibitions across Europe. We close with a brief discussion, incorporating recommendations for similar collaborations in future such projects, and additionally include a series of appendices containing further details on the artworks and the creative processes behind them.

1. Introduction

As part of the TETRARCHs project, the project team collaborated with three creative practitioners/artists to investigate the reuse of archaeological data. These practitioners were recruited, integrated into teams of archaeologists, then created creative works in response to their participation. This report summarises this process.

2. Recruitment

Recruitment of the artists began in February 2023, after discussions during the kick-off meeting and subsequent project meetings to further define their responsibilities. As lead on the TETRARCHs Artist in Residence work package, Colleen Morgan sought training and guidance from the University of York Impact team to ensure that recruitment processes were equitable and compliant with industry standards. Key advice included working with a practising artist to help shape the bid going forward. Sound artist and academic Dr Cobi Van Tonder was engaged to help shape the artist brief and to engage in one of the artist in residence positions. As Van Tonder had previously worked with Morgan, it was assured that there would be some positive outcomes for the project, even if the recruitment processes did not secure artists who were able to fulfil the brief; this was not an issue in the end as all artists engaged and were able to fully participate in the project.

The artist brief (Appendix 1) was drafted by Morgan and distributed to the TETRARCHs team for editing and commentary. Several key themes were identified as important to the brief:

- *What might justice, resistance, insecurity, fear, jealousy, hope, romance, spirituality or courage have looked like in the past?*
- *How have people deceived, coped with, played amongst, desired, envied, betrayed or befriended one another across space and time?*
- *How does loneliness, ambition, prejudice, morality, independence, servitude or freedom manifest in the historical record? How might we deploy this knowledge today to effect pro-social change?*

The fees were set according to the Artists' Union England rates of pay, £255.85 per day, for 30 days of work for artists with 3+ years of experience, with an additional stipend for travel and materials, for up to £12,000 each.

The recruitment process for the TETRARCHs Artist in Residence commenced in May 2023 and closed on 19 June 2023. The opportunity was advertised broadly, across social media and targeted European-wide networks of artists and creatives (Appendix 2).

There were 52 applicants, representing 19 countries, with the majority from England (Fig. 1), perhaps reflecting the location and network of PI Sara Perry, and creatives lead Colleen Morgan.

Fig. 1: Distribution of applicant countries for the artist in residence opportunity.

Ten applicants were longlisted by Holly Wright, Colleen Morgan, Sara Perry, Rimvydas Laužikas, and Cobi Van Tonder. The other work package leaders, Nicolo Dell'Unto, Edisa Lozić, Helene Verreyke, and Christophe Verbruggen were then asked to review this longlist, by the following criteria: 1) Compatibility with your work package, 2) Collaborative potential, 3) Spark - does their application/potential participation spark your interest. Shortly thereafter a shortlist of five were selected for interviews. The shortlisted candidates were selected for their robust applications and representation across Europe. The interviews were conducted according to the standards set forth by the University of York Human Resources guidelines, and a consensus view was reached on the final candidates. Successful applicants were notified on 3 October and we met with them as a team on 3 November to discuss the future of their involvement in the project. The artists selected were Eloise Moody (England), Chloe Dierckx (Belgium), and we retained Cobi Van Tonder (Italy).

After the completion of the selection process, applicants were contacted with the option to join a "Creative Heritage" mailing list, moderated by Morgan, to broadcast other opportunities to work with heritage and archaeology. This group has since grown to 186 members, with ~15 posts per year.

3. Fieldwork

The artists participated in archaeological excavations in three countries, and consulted with Christophe Verbruggen regarding processing digital data in the form of LIDAR.

3.1 Hili Archaeological Park, United Arab Emirates

Cobi Van Tonder joined the second fieldwork season for the University of York Excavations at Hili Archaeological Park, directed by Colleen Morgan in collaboration with the University of Durham and the Abu Dhabi Department of Culture and Tourism (Fig. 2). The fieldwork commenced on 3 January 2024 and lasted for three weeks; Van Tonder joined the project from 12-20 January. The goal of the project was to investigate domestic structures associated with the Umm an-Nar period (c. 3200–2000 BCE) at Hili Archaeological Park in Al Ain, UAE, a UNESCO World Heritage Site. The project seeks to address longstanding gaps in knowledge about everyday life, domestic architecture, and socio-economic organisation in the region. Initial excavations in 2022/3 successfully identified preserved archaeological deposits and features, including mudbrick structures, irrigation systems, and activity areas suggesting cooking and craft production. During the most recent season (2023/4) Van Tonder observed the team analysing materials from previous and recent excavations, conducting targeted excavations and using aerial and terrestrial surveys (Fig. 3).

Fig. 2: Aerial View of the Hili Archaeological Park with Hili 16 in the foreground

Fig. 3: Van Tonder interviewing project member Louise Fowler (MOLA)

The team visited Jebel Hafit Desert Park to examine the many Hafit tombs in the park. While there, Van Tonder conducted a sonic impulse response experiment with team members to record acoustics of the archaeological remains (Figs. 4, 5).

Fig. 4: Cobi Van Tonder, Leila Araar and Louise Fowler conducting the sonic impulse response experiment.

Fig. 5: York at Hili Archaeological Park team photo at Jebel Hafit Desert Park

This first fieldwork experience was greatly informative for the subsequent artist participation at Toumba Serron, as the excavation Director, Morgan, did not have the requisite time to fully support Van Tonder's participation in the excavation. Even though Morgan's work is greatly informed by creative practice and imaginative archaeological interpretation, code-switching between the demands of an excavation in regard to data collection, organisation and pastoral care of all participants and reflective creativity was extremely difficult. This experience may have been somewhat mitigated by a more collectively organised excavation wherein participants were more autonomous. There was also a lack of required background information regarding the site to scaffold more extensive participation in creative interpretation. These factors will be more fully explored in the Discussion section of this report.

3.2 Toumba Serron, Greece

The excavations at Toumba Serron in northern Greece are a collaboration between the University of York and the Ministry of Culture General Directorate of Antiquities and Cultural Heritage, with the permit to work there issued by the British School at Athens. It has been running for five seasons annually between 2020 and 2024. The site of Toumba Serron, a Late Neolithic settlement in Central Macedonia, has been a TETRARCHs case study for three years. It lies in the Strymon valley and provides critical insights into Neolithic social and material practices.

2024 Season

As an integral part of the TETRARCHs project at Toumba Serron in 2024, the team undertook a comprehensive localised stakeholder evaluation to investigate the potential for (re)use of project data, particularly for storytelling. Crucially, this work helped to shape the brief and the community and project touchpoints for the two TETRARCHs Creative Practitioners, Eloise Moody and Chloé Dierckx (accompanied by Morgan, who was present to assist them), who both came to Toumba during 7-22 July 2024 to develop site-specific artistic interventions grounded in local and project priorities, to help demonstrable routes for data reuse (Figs. 6, 7). These insights shaped the focus and formats of the practitioners' 2024 on-site interventions and their subsequent development,

completion and public dissemination, which was completed in the off season and in the run-up to and during the 2025 field season.

Fig. 6: Eloise Moody excavating at Toumba Serron

Fig. 7: Chloe Dierckx sketching at Toumba Serron

2025 Season

Moody returned to Toumba Serron for the next season, working with the team to bury the artwork that she produced, as discussed in section 3, below. She also engaged with a local baker to create bread with conversation prompts to promote exchanges about the site amongst the local community. Dierckx also sent copies of her artwork back to the local community for distribution.

3. Exhibitions

The artists had several opportunities to exhibit their work, both independently and hosted by the TETRARCHS project. The summary of venues and their respective impact is below.

3.1 King's Manor, University of York, United Kingdom

The TETRARCHS exhibition was initially planned to occur in Antwerp, Belgium at the Royal Academy during May 2025. Unfortunately, this was cancelled in March 2025, and while there were many attempts to coordinate another exhibition and while several venues in Antwerp, Athens, and London were explored, it was finally decided to hold a smaller exhibition in June 2025, at the King's Manor, Department of Archaeology, University of York, United Kingdom. Artists Chloé Dierckx and Eloise Moody were able to accommodate this change, whereas Cobi Van Tonder was not able due to a conflict in her schedule. Eloise Moody created a piece titled *All of it Happened and Some of it's True* (Figs. 8, 9), a geotextile with 22ct gold leaf and embroidered with silk, linen, and cotton. From her exhibition interpretation accompanying the piece (Appendix 3):

This embroidery came about after hours of conversations with archaeologists based in the UK and across Europe. If archaeology acts as a lens, helping us understand our past and anchor ourselves in place and time, then shouldn't we turn our attention to the people doing the work? Who are they? What of themselves do they bring to their work? How does working with such long timescales affect how they perceive time in their own lives?

Fig. 8: Eloise Moody, installing artwork at the King's Manor, Department of Archaeology, University of York.

Fig. 9: Eloise Moody's work as installed at the King's Manor, Department of Archaeology, University of York.

Chloé Dierckx created *Sunrises*, a tarot deck with paintings she created in response to the project (Fig. 10). From her exhibition interpretation accompanying the piece (Appendix 4):

Dierckx asked residents the following question: "What object of yours do you think archaeologists of the future will find?". The responses were incorporated into a hand drawn card set, together with drawings of archaeological artefacts and stories. Designed to be reshuffled and rearranged, the cards present a non-linear narrative in which past and present intertwine. Through this, the artist reflects on the continuity and shared experiences of humans across time.

Chloé Dierckx's 2024 residency at Toumba, undertaken within TETRARCHS, brought archaeologists and village residents into conversation. Her aim was to help people in Toumba understand what the excavations were doing in their own community and to strengthen everyday connections to local history. Working alongside the field team, she translated specialist knowledge and site data into formats that could travel beyond the trench, aligning with TETRARCHS' ambition to keep scientific information lively and reusable for wider publics.

Her process combined engagement with Toumba's datasets and on-site discussions with a programme of doorstep conversations in the village. She invited residents to imagine which of their personal belongings might one day be unearthed by archaeologists, using their responses (together with stories from the excavation) to surface the personal meanings that link present lives to the archaeological record. This emphasis on relevance to the people she was working with shaped the content and tone of the work, reinforcing TETRARCHS' community-centred approach to data reuse.

The outcome this year was *Sunrises*: a hand-drawn, tarot-inspired deck of cards that interleaves illustrations of artefacts and field narratives with drawings prompted by local stories; editions of which were disseminated back to the members of the team and community who had inspired it. Designed to be reshuffled, the deck produces non-linear constellations where past and present sit

side by side, encouraging reflection on continuities in human experience and on the futures we hope to carry forward. The title nods both to the early starts of excavation and to the steady cycle of daybreak – an image of constancy against which human histories rise and fall.

Fig. 10: Chloé Dierckx and “Sunrises” at the TETRARCHs exhibition

Fig. 11: Chloé Dierckx discussing her installation in King’s Manor, Department of Archaeology, University of York

The exhibition opened on 6 June, and closed on 7 June. There was a celebratory opening, and the exhibition benefitted from support from EU Cost-Action funded TETRARCHs and the Place and Community Knowledge Exchange Fund - PCKE, an internally-distributed fund at the University of York (£951.11). This fund allowed us to print materials in support of the exhibition, fund the opening, materials for displaying the artwork, and expenses around artist attendance. It also enabled us to provide wages for student exhibition helpers, who also evaluated the exhibition. This evaluation work has contributed toward MSc Digital Heritage student Kasi Zoldoski obtaining a job after graduation. The exhibition launch was attended by 25 people (Fig. 11) and there were 75 people who viewed the exhibition.

Some comments from visitors to the exhibition, gathered in conversation:

"It's detached from its original context, just like archaeology. It makes you wonder what the meaning of the quotes are." - two older women discussing the tapestry

"This had to have taken a really long time!" - seven year old boy

"The questions you ask are as important as the answers." - women speaking to Eloise Moody

The guestbook also garnered several comments (Fig. 12):

"What an incredible and awesome piece of work! The scale and craft of this hanging is beyond words - and, after all that work, to be buried...and fragments as a whole is superb, please can we have more in the future?"

"The way of expressing the archaeology data in a simple, artistic, and easily understandable way for a common person is amazing."

Fig. 12: Comments in the guest book from the exhibition

3.2 London, United Kingdom

Eloise Moody exhibited *All of it Happened and Some of it's True* in London on 19 June as a private viewing.

Fig. 13: Private viewing of Eloise Moody's 'All of it Happened and Some of it's True', London

3.3 Toumba, Greece

Moody returned to Toumba in June/July 2025 with *All of it Happened and Some of it's True* and another artwork, *Breaking Bread*. *All of it Happened and Some of it's True* was displayed at the excavation lab and local residents and dignitaries were invited to the viewing. Around 50-60 people attended. The artwork was then buried in an excavation trench at the end of the season (Figs. 14-16).

Fig. 14: Unfolding the embroidery by Eloise Moody on site, before its final burial

Fig. 15: 'All of it Happened and Some of it's True' in the trench, ready for backfilling.

Fig. 16: Partially backfilled, some of the last words visible on the embroidered geotextile - *“Honestly, I don’t really believe in preservation”*

Moody’s other project, *Breaking Bread*, was aimed at connecting the local community in Toumba with the excavation, although Moody later brought *Breaking Bread* to the excavations in Sardinia as well. Moody worked with Local Bakers, Χρήστο Τούνα, to create 40 special loaves of bread with a small artists’ edition – a handmade and hand-bound booklet with information about the excavation and the artworks as well as 6 questions baked inside (Fig. 17). Moody states (see Appendix 3 for the full artist’s statement):

A small team of archaeologists and I sat across the street, sipping coffees, eating baked goods and generally being present. As customers left the bakery they would point to their bread and wave to us. Often, our lack of shared language meant we could share few words, but as we all waved back enthusiastically, we could feel the small threads of connection weaving between us.

Fig. 17: The baker in Toumba holding one of the bespoke loaves

3.4 Puglia, Italy

Cobi Van Tonder performed her work *Vertical Time* on 16 August 2025 in Puglia, Italy, to 150-200 participants. The work is 45 minutes long and is performed live. From the artist statement accompanying the piece (Appendix 4):

Standing there in Hili16, observing the careful digging and gentle brushing of dust, blowing in the wind, against the dramatic light of the sunrise, this piece was born, with a feeling of time, many- thousand-year-old ghosts, the impossibility of reaching them, except through DNA that may now be in the people of this area, contemplating a 5000 year time window, next jumping in my mind to 5000 years from now – will some AI humanoids be digging out our remains? Will someone be wondering about us?

Vertical Time is above all for me about this, memories and consciousness buried, layer by layer, in the soil with the feeling of our human fragility and human hope and continuous survival juxtaposed against the vertical depth of time. Time, often represented horizontally on classical music scores or on timelines and calendars – in the west often a line flowing from left to right. In stark contrast, this is time buried vertically, in millimeters.

Van Tonder describes the performance as such:

The premiere was a wonderful summer night performance in the garden of the Malacusa House in Fantese, Puglia. With multi-channel surround loudspeakers, I started with the sound of wind in the vast desert, then fading in the singing dunes - deep vibrations around 110 Hz. Gradually I added the surface sounds of archaeologists digging and brushing away at dust, panning these sounds around the audience, with my frequency clusters (a series of 27 combinations) fading, pulsing in and out, at more and more piercing intensity, until they became audio physical full body immersive sound. Later I heard from the owner of the house, my friend Fabio Malacusa, that the neighbors phoned the police during the concert, to report a UFO landing! probably the best compliment a concert can receive! The police told them to report to a psychiatric ward... Overall, a beautiful audience and experience for us all. I hope to repeat this piece soon and in many places.

Fig. 18: Cobi Van Tonder performing *Vertical Time* in Puglia, Italy.

3.5 Palermo, Italy

Van Tonder brought the performance to the Wall of Sounds Festival on 20 December in Palermo, Italy.

Fig. 19: Cobi Van Tonder performing Vertical Time in Palermo

4. Discussion

There are several additional outcomes from WP8 that are more recently completed or in progress. On 17 December, Eloise Moody and James Taylor presented 'Breaking Bread - All of It Happened and Some of It's True: Hospitality as Performance Archaeology at Toumba Serron' as part of the Theoretical Archaeology Group meetings at the University of York, UK in a session: *Performing the Past: Archaeological and Anthropological Perspectives on Performance*. There is also a short film forthcoming from Morgan about the artists' participation in TETRARCHs.

There are many very positive outcomes from artist participation within archaeological projects. In TETRARCHs, the artists acted as translators of archaeological practice, pushed the archaeologists to think in new ways about their practice, and vice versa. There were important relationships built amongst and between artists, archaeologists, and community members, and this is not to be underestimated as a positive result of inclusion of creative practitioners.

Recommendations moving forward include: scaffolding should be developed to aid creative practitioner engagement with archaeology; background knowledge should be more widely distributed amongst participants in archaeological excavations; more egalitarian management structures may support broader engagement with archaeological knowledge production and authentic participation in the interpretation of the past; funding regarding support for artist participation and exhibitions should be ringfenced within projects.

Appendices

Appendix 1: Creative Brief

CREATIVE BRIEF: TETRARCHs

Host organisation:

The Department of Archaeology at the University of York is a top rated archaeology department, located in the centre of historic York, UK. We are developing new methods of exploring and visualising ancient landscapes, excavating sites, analysing ancient artefacts, human and animal bones, pioneering the biomolecular study of all manner of organic and inorganic compounds, and conserving our shared heritage in order to tell diverse stories and build a sustainable future.

<https://www.york.ac.uk/archaeology/>

The Research Project:

TETRARCHs: Transforming Data Reuse in Archaeology is experimenting with ways archaeologists collect data and use that data for storytelling in ways that are meaningful for diverse audiences. It is funded by the Collaboration of Humanities and Social Sciences in Europe CHANSE, which is a joint initiative of 27 research funding organisations from 24 countries, under European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme.

CONSORTIUM:

Sara Perry, Project Leader (MOLA), Holly Wright, Co-I (University of York), Rimvydas Laužikas, PI (Vilnius University), Edisa Lozić, PI (Znanstvenoraziskovalni center Slovenske akademije znanosti in umetnosti), Nicolás Dell'Unto PI (Lund University), Helene Verreyke, PI (University of Antwerp), Christophe Verbruggen (Ghent University)

<https://www.tetrarchs.org/>

[Colleen Morgan](#) (University of York) will be leading this process.

Emergent Themes:

Our project includes archaeology data collection at three different scales – from whole landscapes, to single sites, to individual objects. We'll explore these using four increasingly common technologies for data capture: airborne LiDAR, 3D scanning, digital field drawing and photography.

The following themes have emerged from the current understanding of the project:

- What might justice, resistance, insecurity, fear, jealousy, hope, romance, spirituality or courage have looked like in the past?
- How have people deceived, coped with, played amongst, desired, envied, betrayed or befriended one another across space and time?
- How does loneliness, ambition, prejudice, morality, independence, servitude or freedom manifest in the historical record? How might we deploy this knowledge today to effect pro-social change?

Creative Commission:

TETRARCHs aims to commission 2 creative professionals to work with the TETRARCHs team to co-create and assess the storytelling potential of the optimised data. They will identify archaeological data that is meaningful to their practice and to feed back into the process of archaeological investigation. During this time creatives will attend archaeological excavations, participate in project meetings (10 total virtual partner meetings + 1 in person meeting, expenses paid by TETRARCHs), and use the TETRARCHs resources to undertake original research which will result in a creative output. Creative practitioners will then collaborate on a reflection on their experience in the project for publication in a forum relevant to their practice (e.g., an industry magazine, a local radio programme, a YouTube channel, etc.).

Who Are We Looking For?

We aim to commission creatives working in a range of forms including visual arts, music and sound, film, dance, creative writing, design, photography and other forms. Of particular interest are practitioners who want to explore an interest in archaeology and the past. Good communication skills are essential for this project, as it is highly interactive. Willingness to travel to fieldwork sites is desirable.

Applications are sought from creatives across Europe, with particular attention given to those from or living in the project partner countries (United Kingdom, Sweden, Belgium, Slovenia, and Lithuania). We welcome applicants from all backgrounds, particularly those under-represented in archaeology, and those who self-identify as being from a Black, Asian or Minority Ethnic (BAME/Global Majority) background.

Fees and expenses (per person):

Creative subcontracting: £7675.50; We are matching rates with the [Artists' Union England rates of pay](#), at 255.85 per day, for 30 days of work for artists with 3+ years of experience.

Artists can invoice for a total of up to £12,000 inclusive of VAT over the life of the project to include freelance and short contract employment fees and supplementary costs (such as travel, materials, and other costs associated with the production the creative work). Note that this pay will occur in three tranches, £5,000 at the start of the project, £5,000 at the mid-point, and £2,000 upon completion of the work.

Creative Process Timescale:

May 2023: Creative Brief Circulated

June 19 2023: Deadline for creative proposals. Submissions due by midnight GMT

July 3 2023: Shortlist of creatives will be contacted for interviews

July 17 - 21 2023: Creative professionals will be interviewed

July 24 2023: Commissioned creatives will be notified and briefing sessions will be arranged

July 2023 - March 2024: Commissioned creatives work with researchers to identify elements in archaeological data that correspond to their creative needs

March 2024 - July 2024: Commissioned creatives produce work in response to this data

August 15 2024: Creatives submit final work to TETRARCHs and publish their reflections in relevant outlet

Application Process:

To apply to this opportunity please provide:

- A CV detailing relevant experience
- Examples of previous work
- A one-page expression of interest letter which details:
 - Why you are interested in this project and any previous interest or experience working with archaeological or historical materials
 - A summary or proposal detailing how you will approach this work, including the creative forms you will use
 - Any information about your background relevant to the points outlined in the “who are we looking for” section above
- Details for two referees. These can be other collaborators, instructors, gallery staff, or others who can comment on your background experience.

A selection panel will meet to review the applications and will contact all successful applicants.

If you have not heard from us by 21 July 2023, please assume your application is unsuccessful.

For any further information or to submit your application please email: colleen.morgan@york.ac.uk

All applications must be submitted by midnight BST on 19 June 2024. No late submissions will be accepted.

Appendix 2: Eloise Moody

<http://Eloisemoody.com>

ALL OF IT HAPPENED AND SOME OF IT'S TRUE.

2025. Geotextile, 22ct gold leaf, silk, linen, cotton.

For the last year I have been Artist-in-residence with Tetrarchs archaeologists, where it soon became clear that we were in much the same business: uncovering human stories, connections and illumination. The cakes we bake may be wildly different, but we are most definitely sharing ingredients.

This embroidery came about after hours of conversations with archaeologists based in the UK and across Europe. If archaeology acts as a lens, helping us understand our past and anchor ourselves in place and time, then shouldn't we turn our attention to the people doing the work? Who are they? What of themselves do they bring to their work? How does working with such long timescales affect how they perceive time in their own lives?

At the same time, I became interested in what cannot be collected through archaeology - the nuance in a person's life or way of being, the thoughts, beliefs and small importances that may never be articulated or become tangible. These are the things that animate a person and encourage connection with past lives, but how and when do you collect that and with what accuracy? And so, I started asking questions. Lots of them. The same ones to each archaeologist. Do you feel lucky? Do you daydream? How do you celebrate? How do you console yourself? The generosity and thought that never said to anyone else. This has become an archive of sorts, as well as something of a weather report upon a group of people. By knowing how they all respond to the same questions, you can read the human meteorological conditions.

The title of this piece is borrowed from another phrase, used by the writer Ann Patchett. She says, 'None of it happened and all of it's true.' I have swapped it around into what could be the elevator pitch for archaeology. The other words are all fragments from my conversations with archaeologists – moments of meaning and beauty which expressed nuance that made me sigh with recognition of having uncovered something. All details impossible to find in an excavation.

No matter what my question or their answer is, they amount to the same thing – how do you exist in the daily smaller ways? What stories do you tell yourself? What is important? I've come to believe that even these three questions lead to interchangeable answers. I like to think of these fragments as bits of conversation we are lucky enough to momentarily tune into, allowing us to consider something afresh or even to ask ourselves the better, more potent questions.

And so this embroidery, entirely handstitched in the finest of materials, will soon be travelling to Toumba Serron in Greece where it will be buried in an excavation trench at the end of the season. I like to think of it as a bookmark – in which story, I cannot say. What I do know is that it will be lain directly upon the remains of lives of neolithic people, and that the thoughts, ideas and dreams of those who have been carefully working to interpret the past will lie in the dark, interrupting time's layers. Perhaps it will never be uncovered. Or perhaps in some unknown future, it will be found, and even though the materials will have degraded, and the words become partially or entirely obscured, there will be a team of people, trying their best to make sense of this strange document, pretty sure that they can make out the word daydreaming.

Breaking Bread

In Toumba this year, I also worked on a sister project connecting the local community with the excavation, the archaeologists and their work, and the embroidery. *Breaking Bread* is part of a wider series of work. In Toumba, we worked with the Local Bakers, Χρήστο Τούνα στην Τούμπα Σερρών to create 40 special loaves of bread, sold on the middle Saturday of the excavation season. Baked inside each loaf was a small artists' edition – a handmade and hand-bound booklet with information about the excavation and the artworks as well as 6 questions. Each loaf had a different set of questions – no two were the same – about time and being human. These were selected and curated from the list of questions I had asked each archaeologist during research for the embroidery.

For 1 euro 50, local residents could purchase one of these loaves of bread and be part of a gentle, connective art event. Each loaf was broken open amongst friends and families, across different dining tables throughout the village that day. Although we can never know the details of what was said, we do know that many residents of Toumba Serron were having conversations about humanity and perceptions of time, asking each other as they shared food, questions they may never have asked before.

Rewind back to that morning, when the bakery opened. A small team of archaeologists and I sat across the street, sipping coffees, eating baked goods and generally being present. As customers left the bakery they would point to their bread and wave to us. Often, our lack of shared language meant we could share few words, but as we all waved back enthusiastically, we could feel the small threads of connection weaving between us.

Appendix 3: Chloé Dierckx

<https://www.daniodean.org/chlo%C3%A9-dierckx>

Sunrises

As part of the broader research project *Tetrarchs: Transforming Data Reuse in Archaeology*, Chloé Dierckx collaborated with archaeologists and residents of Toumba Serron, Greece. The artist looked for ways to inform the local community about the archaeological excavations taking place in their village and to make them feel connected to their local history.

Dierckx asked residents the following question: “What object of yours do you think archaeologists of the future will find?”. The responses were incorporated into a hand drawn card set, together with drawings of archaeological artefacts and stories. Designed to be reshuffled and rearranged, the cards present a non-linear narrative in which past and present intertwine. Through this, the artist reflects on the continuity and shared experiences of humans across time.

Inspired by Tarot cards, the deck also invites reflection on the future—on what we hope future generations will continue to share with us.

The title Sunrises not only recalls the early morning excavations, but also gestures to the constancy of the sun’s rise and fall—unaffected by the ebb and flow of human societies.

Please feel free to sit down, browse through the cards, explore connections, or create your own constellations.

Appendix 4: Cobi van Tonder

Premiere for VERTICAL TIME – Cobi van Tonder 16 August 2025

I was commissioned by the Transforming Data Reuse in Archaeology (TETRARCHs) project, by the lead partner from the Department of Archaeology at the University of York, to create the piece which you will hear this evening. TETRARCHs explore ways in which archaeologists collect data and use that data for storytelling in ways that are meaningful for diverse audiences. (It is funded by the Collaboration of Humanities and Social Sciences in Europe CHANSE, which is a joint initiative of 27 research funding organizations from 24 countries, under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program.)

Through the Dept of Archaeology York, in collaboration with the University of Durham, and Abu Dhabi's Department of Culture and Tourism, I was introduced to a project that investigates Bronze Age domestic life at Hili Archaeological Park in Al Ain, UAE—a UNESCO World Heritage Site. The focus is on the Hafit and Umm an-Nar periods (c. 3200–2000 BCE), and address longstanding gaps in knowledge about everyday life, domestic architecture, and socio-economic organization in the region. Initial excavations in 2022/3 successfully identified preserved archaeological deposits and features, including mudbrick structures, irrigation systems, and activity areas suggesting cooking and craft production. During their most recent season (2023/4) I observed them analyzing materials from previous and recent excavations, conducting targeted excavations and using aerial and terrestrial surveys.

Broadly, the Bronze Age in Al Ain began around 3000 BCE, with evidence of agricultural villages emerging. A century or two later, between 2500 and 2000 BCE, Hili's settlement and monumental tomb construction expanded significantly during the peak of the Umm an-Nar era. Hili 16 and its associated tombs and structures date firmly to the Umm an-Nar phase (c. 2700–2000 BCE), making them approximately 4,200–4,700 years old.

Process:

I attended excavations, participated in project meetings and interviewed archaeologists on site. I also made some field recordings of the surrounding area, of the sounds of archaeology itself (mostly digging, tapping, brushing and scratching sounds) and I also recorded the impulse response or echoes of a Falaj water system and some Jebel Hafeet tombs - small, bee-hive-shaped stone structures that represent the earliest Bronze Age burial tradition in southeastern Arabia, marking the beginning of more permanent and ceremonial treatment of the dead. These tombs were often used by mobile pastoralist communities, and their construction signaled a shift toward territorial anchoring and social memory. (Later, during the Umm an-Nar period (c. 2800–2000 BCE), the burial practices changed: tombs became larger, circular, and collective, like those at Hili and Umm an-Nar Island — often reused for generations).

Talking to the archaeology team, I learned about how archaeologists go about documenting the process of excavation, since it is a 'destructive process' as they dig deeper, they destroy the layers that have been before and thus they need to carefully document this. One such process is termed a Harris matrix, and I was very impressed by this system and its possible application to become a musical score of some sort. I observed the intuition the experienced archaeologists develop to distinguish between subtle layers of dust and earth to excavate what was previously a wall of a room or a fireplace, using sound cues through tapping on surfaces to navigate and reveal a structure buried in ~5000 years. Especially this type of site, where the bricks of walls were made from the very same material as that of the sand that buried it in time, and where on top of the bronze age settlement

iron age settlements were developed, the nuances are incredibly delicate and a novice like me, was amazed at observing the archaeologists decipher the cues. During some conversations the part that struck me very deeply was the idea that digging one millimeter could mean digging through a year or in some cases many years of time – of course it's not evenly spread out like that, in a space very little activity happened, it could be different - the rate of sediment accumulation or site formation depends on many factors—climate, human activity, erosion, and natural events like floods or sandstorms. 1 mm of stratified cultural deposit could represent anywhere from a few years (if actively used) to a century (in quiet or abandoned periods). If occupation lasted about 1000 years, then 1m of vertical digging could reveal 1000 years!

Thus, the title for the piece formed: time layered and buried vertically in the soil – relating to the microtonal drone music I developed during my PhD compositional research – which was a shift in musical thinking from horizontal rhythmic and melodic musical motives to a kind of 'frozen' dronelike, minimalist wash of vertical frequency layers, suspended in space. Music that slowly transforms and reveals its internal qualities and micro pulses in time, more like a sunset, like the sky changing subtly than a dramatic musical progression. My personal attraction to this being a search for a kind of silence, like jumping into water, being submerged in an alternate reality.

At the same time, TETRARCHs posed in their proposal that they are interested to let artists reflect on human questions, such as 'What might justice, resistance, insecurity, fear, jealousy, hope, romance, spirituality or courage have looked like in the past?' or 'How have people deceived, coped with, played amongst, desired, envied, betrayed or befriended one another across space and time?' or 'How does loneliness, ambition, prejudice, morality, independence, servitude or freedom manifest in the historical record? How might we deploy this knowledge today to effect pro-social change?'

Standing there in Hili16, observing the careful digging and gentle brushing of dust, blowing in the wind, against the dramatic light of the sunrise, this piece was born, with a feeling of time, many-thousand-year-old ghosts, the impossibility of reaching them, except through DNA that may now be in the people of this area, contemplating a 5000 year time window, next jumping in my mind to 5000 years from now – will some AI humanoids be digging out our remains? Will someone be wondering about us?

Vertical Time is above all for me about this, memories and consciousness buried, layer by layer, in the soil with the feeling of our human fragility and human hope and continuous survival juxtaposed against the vertical depth of time. Time, often represented horizontally on classical music scores or on timelines and calendars – in the west often a line flowing from left to right. In stark contrast, this is time buried vertically, in millimeters.

The poetry of archaeology lies in this. The now, on the surface, the past underground, the future waiting in the heavens. Time also as mathematics and specifically as sound: frequency is calculated as cycles per second. The higher a tone, the more cycles per second. The lower, the bigger the wavelength, with a 3000m wavelength roughly being 10 seconds for a single cycle to complete. So I start to work in abstract frequencies imagining their wavelengths and map out a kind of desert and dunes of sound to reach a feeling of vastness: Al Ain is surrounded by the desert, endless dunes that are in themselves living slow shapeshifting monuments of time. They visually represent giant godlike waves that move over extremely slow time.

The Rub' alKhālī—also known as the Empty Quarter—is the largest continuous sand sea in the world, covering about 650,000 km² across Saudi Arabia, Oman, UAE, and Yemen. Its dunes can soar up to ~250–300 m in height and rest upon landscapes that were once hardened lake beds and salt flats

from up to 6,000 years ago. Within the Rub' al-Khālī, several named dunefields include the Liwa dunes near Abu Dhabi (now often referred to as the Liwa “singing sands”) and the Umm al-Samim margins of Liwa, with their shifting crescent dunes. I would have loved to record them myself, but for now I resort to online recordings of these dunes—features that likely formed over thousands of years or more. Several crescent-shaped dunes in the region (such as those near Mesaieed in Qatar, just north of the Empty Quarter) are known to “sing,” producing booming or humming tones in a range of about 80–120 Hz, with some studies and recordings noting frequencies between 90 and 105 Hz and harmonics around ~450 Hz. These sounds occur during sand avalanches or wind-triggered slides, though it is also possible to “rub” the surface to produce similar bass tones. I need these sounds, for depth and vastness, to surround the close-up surface sounds of digging and excavating.

Vertical Time starts in the desert, with the dunes, with the deep singing bass tones, (as well as synthesized dunes), contrasted against desert wind field recordings, that morphs through various vantage points such as the echo of the tombs and falaj tunnels. Next, slowly in vertical time, layers of abstract frequency clusters are presented – some pitches so high, their wavelengths are as tiny as sand grains, they sting the ears like needles, others manifest as low bass tones. They are created via the phenomenon of difference tone pulsing, ranging from extremely deep tones to extremely high tones – they form pulsing interference patterns. The audience is invited to move around and/or turn their heads to experience the physicality of the sound in the air.

Difference tone pulsing is a fascinating acoustic phenomenon where two slightly different frequencies are played together, producing a third, lower ‘ghost’ tone equal to the difference between them—so if 400 Hz and 410 Hz are sounded, the listener perceives a pulsing 10 Hz tone. This effect can create deep, rhythmic sensations felt throughout the body, especially when used with low-frequency or infrasound tones that travel in powerful waves capable of resonating within large spaces—or even the body itself. In bioresonance practices, this concept is mirrored in ancient traditions like Ayurveda, which describes sound (nāda) as a primal force influencing the chakras; Tibetan singing bowls and Zen bells use harmonic overtones to create entrainment and meditative states; and in Chinese medicine and qigong, specific tones correspond to organ systems and meridians. It is the audio-physical experience of sound as vibration. I choose and play around with clusters of frequencies, based on how they make me feel, how they sound and what they represent.

Vertical Time—into the sand, into memory, into the underlayers of human consciousness.

Time fell downward, like sediment.

TETRARCHs is making archaeological data accessible to a wider range of people.

The project explores how data from excavations and post-excavation research can be used and reused for educational, creative, and other life-enriching purposes. We work collaboratively across a variety of communities to experiment with storytelling about the past.

For heritage professionals, we create new resources for developing and measuring the effectiveness of archaeological data for storytelling.

For memory institutions like museums and cultural centres, we create reference materials to support you using these new resources for storytelling.

For creatives and local citizens, we will create a platform where you can search for and experiment with storytelling about the past.

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